

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 5.4

Plan for Exploitation and Sustainability of Results

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D5.4 – Plan for Exploitation and Sustainability of Results

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the third and final iteration of the inDICES Plan for Exploitation and Sustainability. It presents a concrete strategy for the uptake of the project's results by various stakeholders who will use and further build on them. The consortium has identified **eight key exploitable assets** that encapsulate the research findings and innovations produced during the course of the project. They can be divided into two categories:

- *Knowledge Assets*: Policy and Legal Recommendations, Community Resources for Participatory Activities, Datasets, MOOC;
- *Technological Assets*: inDICES Open Observatory (including the Participatory Space and the Self-Assessment Tool), Visual Analytics Dashboard, Extensions to the Decidim Open Source Software.

The focus of this document is to outline a concrete and realistic approach for the exploitation and sustainability of each asset, including the resources required for their maintenance and partner responsibilities. It draws upon the commitment of individual inDICES consortium partners to actively use the results in future activities as well as the relationships established with external parties who have shown interest in building upon the project's activities.

1 Introduction

inDICES set out with an objective to empower decision-makers and policy makers in the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) to better understand the impact of digitisation with the view to stimulate new strategies to (re)use cultural assets. Through various research activities over the last three years, the project has delivered a number of concrete results - ranging from software and datasets to policy recommendations and methodologies - that directly contribute to this objective.

The goal of this Exploitation and Sustainability Plan is to present a concrete and realistic strategy that will ensure the impact of the project's results beyond its duration. The project's dissemination, communication and outreach efforts have already paved the way for the uptake of these results by relevant stakeholders and helped project partners forge partnerships and raise awareness among communities who can act as early adopters. These efforts have already indicated the project's strong potential.

This document presents a roadmap that will ensure the continued impact of these results towards impact-driven (re)use of digital cultural heritage (CH). More specifically:

- Chapter 2 describes the overall approach that the project partner's defined to ensure a long-term impact of its results;
- Chapter 3 outlines the larger context of the digital cultural heritage sector in which inDICES results will provide added value;
- Chapters 4 and 5 present a detail exploitation and sustainability plan for each of the key assets delivered by the project;
- Chapter 6 discusses next steps for the inDICES brand and communication channels;
- Conclusions can be found in chapter 7.

2 Approach towards Exploitation and Sustainability

The consortium partners have defined an Exploitation and Sustainability strategy that is underpinned by four priorities to maximise the long-term impact of the project's results:

- **Open and Free Access.** inDICES partners are committed to transfer the produced knowledge and resources to other interested entities and groups who can further build on them. To ensure this, all inDICES results are publicly and freely available and, apart from the commercial software component of WLT, they are accessible via open licences.
- **Lowering Entry Barriers.** Knowledge barriers are equally important to overcome in order to secure the impact of the inDICES results. For this reason, partners made a conscious commitment to translate research presented in deliverables and research papers into more accessible formats, such as executive summary publications with key insights, illustrations, infographics, participatory activities around the research outputs on the Open Observatory, etc. Workshops between consortium members and exchanges with external stakeholders ensured that the platform's usability, language level and possible interactions were accessible to all.
- **Amplifier Effect.** The consortium focused on creating an amplifier effect by positioning the project's results in relation to already existing communities, such as the Europeana Network Association or COMMUNIA, and complementary projects, such as [RECHARGE](#) and [reCreating Europe](#). This ensures that the project results do not exist in a vacuum but rather actively build on and complement existing work and are disseminated via well-established channels to reach target audiences.
- **Key Stakeholder Commitment.** Throughout the duration of the project, the consortium has invested significant efforts in building relationships with complementary projects and communities - including [Memorandums of Understanding](#) and joint events (see for instance, [an event on intellectual property rights](#)). To ensure the interest and investment from various stakeholders, the project has identified seven clearly defined exploitable assets with a convincing unique value proposition for specific target groups.

2.1 Business Model Canvas and Unique Value Proposition

During the course of the project, a Business Model Canvas (BMC) was used to map key propositions of the project and appropriate instruments to support their exploitation to the right audiences.¹ Figure 1 presents the final iteration of the BMC with an outlook towards the future sustainability of the inDICES results. It can

¹ <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>

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be used as a high-level overview of the Exploitation and Sustainability strategy that captures its crucial elements. Note that the BMC model uses language (e.g. customers, revenue streams) that is tailored for the commercial sector rather than the not-for-profit context in which most of the inDICES results will be exploited. For the purposes of this exercise, we maintained the original language of the model. “Customers” in the context of this exploitation and sustainability plan can be defined as key beneficiaries and “revenue streams” refer to funding acquired to support the presented activities rather than a plan to generate earnings.

Complementing the BMC, table 1.1 below presents how various project’s results present a unique value proposition to specific target groups.

Figure 1 - Final iteration of the inDICES Business Model Canvas

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At the centre of the BMC are the inDICES key propositions - **seven key exploitable assets** which have been grouped in two categories - (i) knowledge assets that introduce novel methodological and policy frameworks as well as training and upskilling resources, and (ii) technological assets - software components that enable data-driven decision making and participatory processes. These assets present a unique value proposition towards **seven specific customer segments**. Over the last three years, inDICES has invested significant efforts in building relationships with its **primary customers** via activities such as training workshops for young professionals, events directed at policy makers, and activities co-organised with special interest groups such as COMMUNIA. This has ensured that the project's results are in line with the needs and expectations of these groups. Next to the primary customer groups, **two secondary groups** will also gain new opportunities through the project - creative industries will benefit from improved conditions for digital heritage reuse and communities working with the Decidim open source technologies will benefit from new features to facilitate participatory processes.

The Exploitation and Sustainability strategy relies on the participation of a number of **key stakeholders**. All consortium members have expressed clear commitment to exploit, maintain and further develop the project's results. The strength of the consortium lies in the fact that each partner is well connected to strategically important actors who are shaping the digital cultural heritage landscape - including the Europeana Initiative (the Foundation, Network Association and Aggregator Forum), various heritage networks and research groups - which have been engaged and will be further activated to support and participate in a number of **key activities**. They will take part in and over time initiate their own participatory activities on the Open Observatory. They will use the knowledge assets produced by inDICES in policy advocacy work and for capacity building activities. The project has delivered **key resources** to support this - consortium partners have taken on the role of the Open Observatory Ambassadors to support moderation and governance on the platform, onboarding resources and technical document will support the adoption of the project's technical assets, and the commitment of various communities will ensure that the knowledge assets are being actively implemented.

To create the intended amplifier effect, key partners will continue **building relationships** with the identified customer groups via complementary networks, ongoing and future projects. The brands of consortium partners and their networks (e.g. NEMO) will be used as outreach **channels**. The **costs** for sustaining and promoting the project's results (primarily hosting costs for technical assets and human resources for maintaining them and supporting their active use) will be supported by **revenue streams** from already ongoing and related projects on a European or national level (e.g. RECHARGE; more detail on complementary projects is provided in chapters that follow).

Table 1.1 Summary of the inDICEs unique value proposition for various target groups.

Stakeholder Group	Value Proposition	inDICEs Results	Key Actions to Support Exploitation
Cultural heritage practitioners - currently working professionals and students preparing to work in the field	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upskill and acquire new knowledge on the impact and potential of digital transformation; - Gain a practical understanding on how to design activities for participatory engagement with digital cultural heritage; - Learn how to follow copyright regulations and take advantage of various exceptions in your digitisation and public engagement efforts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community Resources for Participatory Activities, especially the Change Impact Assessment Framework, Copyright Guide, Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation); - MOOC - a training resource for cultural heritage professionals, providing a comprehensive understanding on the role of digital transformation in the sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion via existing heritage networks and partner activities.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute to participatory activities and deliberation processes that influence decisions about the future of the sector; - Network and create communities with other professionals who face the same challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Observatory - an online space that allows users to take part in as well as initiate their own participatory activities (debates, consultations, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participatory activities initiated among project partners and stakeholders, for example within the Europeana Initiative.
Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquire strategies and tools to measure and improve the impact of their activities; - Gain a better understanding of the current trends and debates in the field. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change Impact Assessment Framework provides a methodological foundation for organisations aiming to improve their impact; - Self-Assessment Tool - an instrument that can be used by organisations to assess their strategies; - Visual Analytics Dashboard gives insights into trends that should be considered in organisational discussions and strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued use of the ENUMERATE Self-Assessment Tool; - Promotion via existing heritage networks and partner activities.

Stakeholder Group	Value Proposition	inDICEs Results	Key Actions to Support Exploitation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement strategies and policy to increase the reuse and impact of your digital collections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy and legal recommendations presenting strategies on how to improve conditions for cultural heritage reuse and participatory culture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future advocacy efforts by consortium partners within ongoing and future projects and initiatives.
Policymakers - at a European and national levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement policies and instruments that allow for new uses of cultural heritage by the creative industries or communities and that enhance the societal impact of digital cultural heritage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy and legal recommendations outlining concrete conditions and changes that are needed to ensure that CHIs fulfil their public mission. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advocacy by consortium partners and related networks towards European ministries and policy makers at the national level.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gain evidence- and data-based insights into the needs of the sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Observatory - the participatory activities on the platform provide a bottom-up mechanism to gather data about challenges and needs in the sector; - Visual Analytics Dashboard embedded on the Open Observatory offers a way to monitor trends in the sector that might require new support instruments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of participatory activities via partner channels.
Special interest groups - networks and associations active and related to the digital heritage field, such as COMMUNIA, Europeana Network Association, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support their advocacy effort through better insights into the needs and challenges in the sector; - Initiate participatory activities to activate stakeholder involvement around various (policy-related) topics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Observatory provides an open space to engage with a variety of stakeholders in transparent deliberation processes and use participatory processes to gather data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uptake of the results in related projects; - Promotion of participatory activities via partner channels.

Stakeholder Group	Value Proposition	inDICEs Results	Key Actions to Support Exploitation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advocate for community-endorsed policy changes that stimulate open culture, cultural heritage reuse and targeted upskilling of CH professionals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy and legal recommendations that have been formulated and validated through bottom-up processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active partner participation (e.g. of ambassadors) in interest groups and projects (such as COMMUNIA) to promote the adoption of the inDICEs recommendations.
Researchers - those studying the field of cultural heritage and cultural participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gain access to quantitative and qualitative data to support their research on digital transformation in the cultural heritage sector; - Observe and learn about recent trends influencing the cultural heritage sector; - Formulate, develop and collaborate on new hypotheses and research questions. - Access a network of cultural heritage practitioners and communities to work with. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual Analytics Dashboard provides data visualisations of topics of high relevance in the sector. Especially the full version of the dashboard with advanced functionalities for data analysis will support complex research queries; - Community Resources for Participatory Activities, especially the Hypotheses and Insights Assembly and the inDICEs Datasets Assembly, will be of high relevance to researchers who want to develop hypotheses and find relevant data to test them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outreach to relevant stakeholders across the Europeana Initiative (e.g. Europeana Research Community); - Promoting the use of the Hypotheses and Insights Assembly and the inDICEs Datasets Assembly to support activities in current and future research projects.
Creative industries - creative companies, artists and amateur creators who are interested in reusing cultural heritage collections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benefit from improved conditions to collaborate with CHIs and reuse digital heritage collections. - Learn about how to navigate copyright frameworks to reuse digital cultural heritage and find professionals who can help you. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy and legal recommendations will create more favourable conditions for cultural heritage reuse in creative contexts; - Open Observatory provides a way for creative industry representatives to have their voices heard in discussions and decision making processes about cultural heritage reuse. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued pursuit of the project's focus on digital heritage reuse in future projects; - Awareness building via outreach activities of ongoing and future projects.

Stakeholder Group	Value Proposition	inDICEs Results	Key Actions to Support Exploitation
<p>Decidim and Open Source Community - developers, participants of the Decidim-based platforms</p>	<p>- Gain access to new functionalities to support participatory engagement on the Decidim platform.</p>	<p>- Extensions to the Decidim Open Source Software, such as the Custom Proposal component, which is already used by almost 75% of the Decidim instances active in Europe, and the Self Assessment Tool, which will be made available as a Decidim plug-in to the Decidim community.</p>	<p>- Active participation in the Decidim community Forums; - Public presentation of inDICEs Observatory and related developments at Decidim annual event</p>

3 inDICES in the Context of Future Developments for the Cultural Heritage Sector

inDICES responded to the call with the identifier “DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019”, published by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 Programme. The call text stipulates that “By providing qualitative and quantitative analysis and by proposing solutions, business models and policy recommendations, the action will contribute to a better understanding of regulation and **fairer accessibility of digitised cultural goods** and services. It will also advise on appropriate levels of **harmonisation of copyright and IPR**, thereby contributing to the development and deepening of the **Digital Single Market**.”²

Since the call was released, the European Commission and other stakeholders have continued to develop policies in the three areas mentioned in the call:

1. Development of the Digital Single Market
2. Accessibility of digitised cultural goods
3. Harmonisation of copyright and IPR

inDICES has continuously followed these developments, thus ensuring that the Recommendations (as listed in Section 4.4 below) are aligned with most current policy developments as well as related work by projects and initiatives such as ReCreating Europe³, COMMUNIA⁴ and Creative Commons. Below, the most relevant developments for each of the three areas is summarised.

3.1 Development of the Digital Single Market

The European Commission’s European Strategy for data⁵ aims to deliver digital transformation at scale through a coherent and synergistic approach across framework programmes. The European strategy for data aims at creating a single market⁶ for data that will ensure Europe’s global competitiveness and data sovereignty.

In line with some of the principles defended by the Open Data Directives⁷, the European Strategy for Data acknowledges the value of the reusability of the data by everyone, regardless of whether it is generated by the public or the private sector. The Strategy has a direct impact on digital cultural heritage. There is, for

² https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019

³ <https://www.recreating.eu/>

⁴ <https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendations/>

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021SC0351>

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/legislation-open-data>

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example, explicit mention of the value of public sector data, produced with public funds, and the need for it to benefit society at large by opening it up, in line with a long-standing EU policy objective in that area. The Strategy makes numerous references to the need to balance out the push for a ‘data-agile economy’ with ‘respecting and promoting the fundamental values that are the foundation of European societies’, and is described as defending ‘the best of Europe - open, fair, diverse, democratic, and confident’.

Common European data spaces will ensure that more data becomes available for use in the economy and society, while keeping companies and individuals who generate the data in control. They aim to create a trusted and interoperable environment that promotes and facilitates the sharing and reuse of data, creating meaningful connections across and between data spaces⁸. The ability to process vast volumes of data is one of the key enablers for other technological developments, supporting the competitiveness of the EU’s industrial ecosystems. This is also an essential condition for the successful deployment of data spaces in several sectors as announced in the proposal for the 2030 Policy “Path to the Digital Decade”.

The European Commission’s Recommendation on a common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage enables⁹ such an environment for European cultural content - making high-value cultural datasets available for re-use, including for conducting research, and allowing cultural sector stakeholders to further enlarge, use and benefit from this data space. Other data spaces relevant to the work of inDICES are: The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the Data Space for Media and the Data Space for Tourism. Europeana, the European digital cultural platform, will be deploying the common data space for cultural heritage. Europeana has led to the unprecedented development of interoperable models, licences and frameworks that already do so much to foster the quality, sharing and reuse of data and which, critically, have been developed in close collaboration with the sector.

Next to establishing data spaces in various economic sectors as part of the data strategy and supporting a Data Spaces Support Centre¹⁰, the European Commission also develops supporting policies. Notably through the Next Generation Internet (NGI) initiative, that aims to ensure that the foundations of the internet are secure and sustainable and aligned with European values of openness. This is key as “Europe enters the Digital Decade with a focus on recovery from a global pandemic, NGI Internet innovations consider people’s privacy concerns first and foremost, for an Internet we can trust laying the groundwork of a Europe that is fit for the Digital Age.”¹¹ Several civic society driven initiatives also support actions towards public-values based architectures, including SDEPS initiative, the coalition of organisations and initiatives united in our

⁸ <https://dssc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Starterkit-Interim-Version-Release-19-Dec-2022.pdf>

⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-proposes-common-european-data-space-cultural-heritage>

¹⁰ <https://dssc.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.ngi.eu/about/>

desire to build a Shared Digital European Public Sphere^{12,13}. Several inDICES consortium partners are part of SDEPS and use their position to bring the most relevant inDICES recommendations related to ecosystems based on public values to the fore. For instance, the Consultation on a “Declaration of Digital Principles”¹⁴ reforming the EU copyright framework supporting universal access to cultural heritage online. The Declaration mentions how “Everyone should have access to a trustworthy, diverse and multilingual online environment and should know who owns or controls the services they are using. This encourages pluralistic public debate and participation in democracy.” This principle is in line with inDICES recommendations, especially “recommendation #4 Make the heritage sector a pillar of the European digital public space”. Also, Civil society organisations (including inDICES consortium partner Europeana Foundation) have recently spoken out to European policymakers to put Digital Commons at the centre of the EU’s digital strategy¹⁵ in the “Civil Society Statement on democratic digital infrastructure calling for “Building Digital Public Spaces that can function as alternatives for the centralised, commercial platforms of today must be at the core of the European Union's digital policies in the coming years”¹⁶. The Open Future Foundation published its “European Public Digital Infrastructure Fund White Paper”¹⁷; it makes the case to launch a fund to support the emergence and maintenance of Digital Public Spaces in Europe by investing in the creation and maintenance of Public Digital Infrastructures, to be secured from the EU budget. If realised, this fund will have a massive impact on reaching the ambitions formulated in the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade as mentioned above. The White paper suggests that Member States that are already committed to supporting a Public Digital Infrastructure fund should examine the possibility of setting up an initial version of the fund, well ahead of the next EU budget cycle.

3.2 Accessibility of digitised cultural goods

The deployment of a common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (by Europeana) through the Digital Europe Programme¹⁸, as outlined above, will serve as the foundation for sharing digitised heritage objects. The fact that access to cultural heritage objects is now embedded in the wider Strategy for Data is an opportunity for the cultural heritage sector: its data is part of a key strategic vision, attracting new ideas, partners, investment, infrastructure, and, above all, joint efforts to have a bigger impact. The sector can

¹² <http://shared-digital.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.sdeps.eu/our-vision/>

¹⁴ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/consultation-on-a-declaration-of-digital-principles>

¹⁵

<https://www.euractiv.com/section/digital/opinion/digital-commons-are-a-pillar-of-european-digital-sovereignty-heres-how-to-support-them/>

¹⁶ <https://cryptpad.fr/pad/#/2/pad/edit/BypQub1y67kij6pJRNfEmBF0S/>

¹⁷ <https://openfuture.pubpub.org/pub/public-digital-infra-fund-whitepaper/release/2>

¹⁸

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2021.166.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AL%3A2021%3A166%3ATOCD#d1e32-28-1

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shape the actions foreseen in the European Strategy for Data on the basis of the values and principles it defends, and its experience in defending public interest objectives. This can be done through publishing recommendations (See Chapter 4.4), active participation in consultations and by contributing to defining high value data sets and the formulation of data governance requirements, to influence policy making across data spaces.

In its Recommendation on a European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, the EC encourages Member States to “put in place appropriate frameworks to enhance the recovery and transformation of the cultural heritage sector and to support cultural heritage institutions in becoming more empowered and more resilient in the future”¹⁹, not only to contribute to digitisation, reuse and digital preservation efforts, but also to have spillover effects in other key sectors of the European economy, such as tourism, research, and other cultural and creative sectors.

Next to investments directly connected to the Strategy for Data (through supporting the Data Space for Cultural Heritage) and calls to Member States to make investments in the sector, for instance by using the Recovery Funds, the EC is also investing in supporting research infrastructures that enable access to cultural heritage assets. In 2022, the EU (DG RTD) published the Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage (ECCCH)²⁰. In it, a group of experts, most of them with a heritage science background, describe the current landscape of pan-EU infrastructures (including E-RIHS, D4Science, DARIAH, CLARIN and EOSC) for the distribution of cultural heritage objects from European CHIs. They outline how a new joint infrastructure can support collaboration between researchers and other heritage professionals. Following the publication of report, the EC published a press release, mentioning how the Collaborative Cloud enables “unprecedented transdisciplinary and large-scale collaboration between specialists, such as cultural heritage scholars, curators, archivists and conservators.” and will offer “technologies for digitising artefacts, researching artworks, and documenting data, all of which will significantly advance and add a new digital dimension to cultural heritage preservation, conservation, and restoration.”²¹ The ECCCH will be funded through the Horizon Europe programme, with calls closing in 2023 and 2024 for an envisaged budget of €110 million. To ensure that the investments will be aligned with needs from the sector, the EC launched a survey to which over 1.000 experts sent detailed replies. According to the report, interactive collaboration ranks the highest among the declared goals of the ECCCH initiative. Specifically, “tools for creating, sharing and re-using interactive content on the Cloud (43.3%); tools for AI-assisted metadata enrichment i.e. to

¹⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/deployment-common-european-data-space-cultural-heritage>

²⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Brunet, P., De Luca, L., Hyvönen, E., et al., Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage : ex – ante impact assessment, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/64014>

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_3855

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make CH content interoperable (37%); tools for advanced interaction with the digital content of the Cloud (36.4%) and tools for analysing, designing and testing interactions with visitors (33.6%).”²²

The ECCCH is part of the “Creativity, Cultural Heritage and Inclusion” cluster in Horizon Europe, aimed to support European cultural heritage to become green and digital. Other noteworthy actions in this cluster relevant in the context of inDICES are:

1. The New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative, the flagship of the EU, has created a broad community of 600 official partner organisations and citizens all around Europe. It gives space for creation and experimentation founded on:
 - aesthetics, quality of experience and style, beyond functionality;
 - sustainability, from climate goals, to circularity, zero pollution, and biodiversity;
 - inclusion, from valuing diversity and equality for all to securing accessibility and affordability.

The initiative's first two year progress report highlights how “The initiative is bringing together people from various backgrounds - from art and design, cultural and creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, to educators, scientists and innovators, businesses, local and regional authorities, and citizen initiatives.”²³ More and more CHIs are including the NEB principles in their programming. The recently published NEB Compass²⁴ allows organisations to test their NEB ambitions with the project examples and guiding questions as reference material. This is relevant, especially for CHIs that are planning to engage with NEB and are looking for examples and a framework to integrate NEB principles into their strategies. inDICES Policy Recommendations²⁵ (especially #2 Empower democratic and community-focused cultural heritage institutions) are aligned with the NEB principles. Horizon Europe Mission and Clusters in 2023 and 2024 will allocate more than €106 million to NEB dedicated calls.

2. The EIT Culture and Creativity. The EIT Culture & Creativity is the Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC) supported by the European Institute for Technology. One of the aims is to connect creatives and organisations. The new pan-European partnership can expect to split approximately EUR 150 million of EIT funding under Horizon Europe with the possibility to leverage more funds from the private and public sector. Several inDICES partners (KUL, EF and NISV) are part of the

²² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Stakeholders’ survey on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage : report on the online survey results, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/691331>

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_23_203

²⁴ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/system/files/2023-01/NEB_Compass_V_4.pdf

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7500883#.ZAS88-zMI3I> and <https://zenodo.org/record/7500839#.ZAS--zMI3I>

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community. The EIT Culture and Creativity focuses on catalysing the power of specific key sectors in the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries (CCSI): Culture Heritage and Crafts, Media and Audio-visual, Gaming, Architecture & Design and Fashion; enablers for the Triple Transitions in its ten action programmes. Three are connected especially closely to inDICES and affiliated consortium partners will ensure inDICES results will be taken on board as the KIC shapes its activities in 2023, the start up year of the multi-year programme. This will be done through participation in so-called Strategic Topic Groups and direct involvement in three Action Programmes:

- *AP2 Skills Fitter*: Equipping the workforce with skills to innovate and create novel solutions through the development of a catalogue of lifelong learning opportunities for upskilling and reskilling professionals in Europe. The Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation²⁶ and the inDICES MOOC is especially relevant in this context.
- *AP9 Knowledge Tank*: Innovating evaluation to enhance the (self-) understanding of CCSI in policy and research. By designing a comprehensive framework for CCSI monitoring, analysis, impact evaluation, including in cross-border and cross-sectoral interactions, building on and interoperable with existing recognised, standardised international models. The inDICES research on the Change Impact Assessment Framework²⁷ will be especially relevant.
- *AP10 Policy Optimiser*: – Supporting policy makers in making frameworks to optimally position the European CCSI in a global landscape. In this context, the inDICES work on legal recommendations²⁸ and policy brief “Towards Community-Focused Cultural Heritage Institutions Operating in the Digital Realm”²⁹ are of particular interest.

Next to the work funded as part of Digital Europe (deployment of the Data Spaces) and Horizon Europe (research and the EIT KIC), actions to support the cultural heritage sector are also included in the Creative Europe Programme, Erasmus+, Europe for Citizens and European Structural and Investment Funds³⁰.

Besides initiatives directly funded by the EU outlined above, a number of additional initiatives are relevant in the context of inDICES research and policy making. Four are listed below:

- The European Heritage Alliance published the Manifesto “Cultural Heritage: a powerful catalyst for the future of Europe” in 2020. Representatives of major European and international heritage

²⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/5666910#.ZATftezMI3m>

²⁷ <https://indices-culture.eu/elementor-2827/>

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/7603214#.ZATfiuzMI3l>

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7500839#.ZATf8ezMI3l>

³⁰ <https://culture.ec.europa.eu/policies/selected-themes/cultural-heritage>

networks which form part of the European Heritage Alliance express the readiness of the wider heritage world to contribute to Europe's immediate social and economic recovery, as well as to the longer-term advancement of the European project. The manifesto lists seven ways in which cultural heritage can act as a catalyst for positive change, one of them "Digitally Transforming Europe" is very much aligned with the work of inDICES, notably on upskilling and knowledge sharing. The manifesto mentions "we must narrow the divide between institutions that are digitally equipped, and those that are not. We need to democratise access to our heritage to support diversity, inclusivity, creativity, and critical engagement in education and knowledge sharing." Both the work in Self Assessment and the inDICES MOOC will prove effective in addressing the digital divide.

- The EU Work Plan for Culture 2023-2026, was adopted by the Council of Culture Ministers of the European Union at the end of 2022. The document will shape EU cooperation on culture for the next 4 years. The resolution on the EU Work Plan focuses on 4 different but complementary priorities: (1) Artists and cultural professionals: empowering the cultural and creative sectors (2) Culture for the people: enhancing cultural participation and the role of culture in society (3) Culture for the planet: unleashing the power of culture (4) Culture for co-creative partnerships: strengthening the cultural dimension of the EU external relations. The connection with inDICES is especially apparent in the area of cultural participation. The resolution mentions the need to provide "affordable or free access to knowledge and information, in full respect of intellectual property rights, enhancing media literacy, creating common ground for dialogue and debate".
- The Extraordinary General Assembly of the International Council of Museums (ICOM) approved a new museum definition in the summer of 2022. It reads: "A museum is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing."³¹ The new emphasis on participation of communities and reflection is in line with the inDICES research work on how digital active cultural participation has a fundamental role on participants in a wide spectrum of psycho-social, environmental and innovation areas³².
- This holistic approach towards the role of culture found in the new museum definition is also echoed in the "European framework for action on cultural heritage"³³ that puts forward five pillars of actions with a corresponding set of activities to fully unleash the impact of cultural heritage for an inclusive, sustainable, resilient, and innovative Europe and stronger global partnerships. These

³¹ <https://icom.museum/en/news/icom-approves-a-new-museum-definition/>

³² <https://indices-culture.eu/elementor-2827/>

³³ <http://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/2317/1/NC0319331ENN.en.pdf>

actions present a concrete pathway for the transformation of the heritage sector and highlight the undoubtedly positive impacts of culture.

3.3 Harmonisation of copyright and IPR

The Directive on open data and the re-use of public sector information, also known as the Open Data Directive, entered into force on 16 July 2019, replacing the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive³⁴. It brings forward measures favouring the sharing and reuse of data generated by the public sector. Under the earlier mentioned European Strategy for Data, the European Union establishes additional priorities, such as incentivising the sharing of data from the private sector too, and new projects, such as the Common European Data Spaces as listed above. Content held by museums, libraries and archives also falls within the scope of application of the PSI Directive since the revision in 2013.

Three additional legislative measures are foreseen that are relevant in the context of inDICES, some of which have been adopted already, that pave the way for these priorities to succeed. These are (i) the Data Governance Act (DGA)³⁵ was adopted in May 2022 to facilitate cross-border use of data, interoperability and standardisation, in particular in the common European data spaces, and finding inspiration in the FAIR principles. (ii) the Data Act (DA)³⁶, currently under discussion at the European Council, will be adopted to incentivise data sharing across sectors. (iii) The Act on high-value datasets seeks to push for more high-quality public sector data to be made available for reuse. This policy work on copyright legislation as well as the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles³⁷³⁸ influences access to cultural heritage. In Section 4.1 below, we outline how the inDICES legal recommendation and legislative EU measures are connected.

We conclude this chapter by mentioning the work of three prominent initiatives that represent the voice of public stakeholders (such as heritage organisations) in consultations that inform future legislation on harmonisation of copyright and IPR.

- The reCreating Europe project released its Final Policy Recommendations for EU Lawmakers³⁹ early 2023. The six policy recommendations include calls to boost the EU role in cultural heritage policy and law making, to reform the EU copyright framework and to clarify and simplify EU role in cultural heritage policy and law making. Also, reCreating Europe is launching an online resource, called

³⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/legislation-open-data>

³⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868>

³⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/data-act-proposal-regulation-harmonised-rules-fair-access-and-use-data>

³⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-principles>

³⁸ <https://openfuture.eu/blog/a-right-to-participation-in-the-digital-public-space/>

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7544364#.ZATVqOzMI3I>

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Copyright Flexibilities⁴⁰ which is "free access to a comprehensive, updated database of copyright exceptions, limitations and other balancing tools from the EU and all 27 Member States, to a wide range of comparative reports on different categories of copyright flexibilities, and to catchy data visualisation." inDICES connects this resource to our Copyright Guide as much as possible. These are very much aligned with the legal recommendations of inDICES. As one of the concrete outcomes of concertation efforts between the projects, the manifesto "The Public Mission of Cultural Heritage Institutions in the Digital Age" has been written.

- The COMMUNIA network published 20 [Policy Recommendations for the Public Domain](https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendations/) developed in May 2022. They identify possibilities for reshaping copyright in ways that expand the public domain and strengthen the rights of users and all types of cultural creators. It contributes to "a copyright framework that maximises societal benefits by embracing the possibilities for wider access to knowledge and culture in an increasingly digitised environment."⁴¹ Some of the policy recommendations address Cultural Heritage Institutions specifically, for instance, the recommendation "to make it mandatory for Member States to protect users and institutions acting with non-commercial purposes from claims for damages for infringement of copyright"⁴², the prohibition of using geoblocking of public domain works⁴³ and supporting cultural practices that require the use and/or remix of parts of protected materials in accordance with fair practice⁴⁴.
- [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/2022/04/04/cc-publishes-policy-paper-titled-towards-better-sharing-of-cultural-heritage-an-agenda-for-copyright-reform/) recently finished research⁴⁵ on what barriers exist for CHIs to make their collections. It lists five concrete actions to achieve this necessary change: (1) Protect the public domain from erosion (2) Reduce the term of copyright protection (3) Legally allow necessary activities of cultural heritage institutions (4) Shield cultural heritage institutions from liability (5) Ensure respect, equity, diversity and inclusivity.

The nature of the collaboration between inDICES and these above mentioned initiatives differ: there have been continuous exchanges between the groups and all of them presented their work at the final inDICES event. The collaboration with reCreating Europe went further and resulted in joint intellectual outcomes, such as the manifesto.

⁴⁰ <http://www.copyrightflexibilities.eu/>

⁴¹ <https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendations/>

⁴² <https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendation/users-who-act-in-reasonable-belief-that-their-uses-of-copyrighted-materials-are-permitted-should-not-face-damages/>

⁴³ <https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendation/geo-blocking-for-audiovisual-works-should-be-prohibited/>

⁴⁴ <https://communia-association.org/policy-recommendation/the-freedom-to-create-should-be-protected-at-the-eu-level/>

⁴⁵

<https://creativecommons.org/2022/04/04/cc-publishes-policy-paper-titled-towards-better-sharing-of-cultural-heritage-an-agenda-for-copyright-reform/>

4 Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy of Knowledge Assets

4.1 Policy and Legal Recommendations

inDICES has delivered the following policy recommendations:

- **Policy Brief: Towards community-focused cultural heritage institutions in the digital realm (D3.6)** - a set of policy recommendations designed to assist cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) in fulfilling their public mission in the digital realm. Its goal is to further the democratic and community-focused digital transformation of CHIs, and to support access to, and the reusability of digital cultural heritage;
- **A white paper with legal recommendations (D3.5)** - a proposal to change the copyright system at the European level, consisting in an introduction of a European regulation instrument for ensuring access and (re)use of cultural heritage resources.

The main aim of the policy work executed in inDICES was to add an additional voice to the ongoing European debate on the role of culture and cultural heritage in the dynamically evolving, blended reality. The recommendations - the broad ones, as well as those focusing on legal issues - are envisioned to assist cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) in embracing their public mission in the digital realm. inDICES perspective pushes for a comprehensive recognition of the social impact of the heritage sector on the society. The project also advocates for a continuous dialogue on further European policy reform leading to better access, sharing, use, and reuse of cultural heritage - one of the critical elements for creating and maintaining a resilient, democratic and sustainable society.

The policy discussion continues after the project reaches its end in March 2023. Chapter three of this document gives an overview of key policy areas and regulations relevant for the project's scope. As the issues raised by inDICES remain pertinent to the EU policy debate, they will be taken on and further exploited by individual project partners and their networks - institutions like FCC, ICCU, MCA, NEMO, EF, NISV and EFHA who have policy work encoded in their organisational strategies. As long-standing professional partners they also tend to work together to support a shared cause.

The partners will keep employing the inDICES policy agenda points elaborated around the fifteen recommendations and legal recommendations to support their discussions with policy makers on national and/or EU levels. Some specific short and long term plans for exploiting the inDICES legacy include:

ADVOCACY:

- The recommendations will be addressed to the relevant European ministries in the framework of the actions linked to the **Work Plan for Culture**, to the evaluations of the Horizon Europe programme, at the national level in order to be taken into account in the framework of digital policies linked to the European recommendations. This will also be addressed to the EC as a contribution to the design of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (MCA). They will also be actively promoted to the European museum landscape, to use them on national, regional and local level to address their policy makers and other stakeholders involved.
- **ekip project** - *ekip* is a Horizon Europe project set to launch in June 2023 that will establish a network-driven policy recommendation engine to continuously drive the formulation and adoption of policy development recommendations for Europe's cultural and creative industries.⁴⁶ As one of the key partners in the consortium, NISV will amplify the needs of cultural heritage organisations in the policy discussions. The foundation for this will be the recommendations and the expert network developed in inDICES. The project will provide opportunities not only to propose recommendations but also test them and put them into practice. inDICES consortium partners will be invited to join the *ekip* network and the project's various activities. The project will work in close collaboration with the EIT Culture and Creativity Knowledge and Innovation Community to ensure alignment of efforts (NISV).
- inDICES policy recommendations will enrich policy and advocacy agendas of **COMMUNIA, Creative Commons Open Culture, the Europeana Copyright Community** and **Knowledge Rights 21** - international networks of activists, researchers and practitioners aiming to promote open culture and knowledge, and eliminate unnecessary restrictions on access and use (FCC).
- inDICES policy recommendations will be proposed and presented within the [Culture Next](#), a network of 32 cities that is to support current and former European Capital of Culture candidate cities to implement culture-led urban development programmes and policies. CCC will create awareness and encourage the member cities to consider in their approach the reuse of digital cultural heritage, by emphasising the benefits it could bring for the member cities (CCC).
- inDICES policy and legal recommendations will be disseminated and presented to the **EC-Heritage Expert group** which brings together European and international cultural networks and representatives of ministries of culture from Europe. NEMO, MCA and EF are members.
- inDICES policy recommendations will be presented as well to 2 major european network: the **Culture Action Europe** - major advocacy network for the culture in the european debate (MCA and

⁴⁶ <https://www.lunduniversity.lu.se/article/new-innovation-policies-will-support-ecosystems-creatives>

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EFHA are members) and to **ENCACT - European network on cultural management and policy** (MCA is member) - in order to contribute to professionals and policy adoption of the recommendations.

IMPLEMENTATION:

- **EIT Culture and Creativity** - the Policy Club format (part of AP10 Policy Optimiser) will be used to incorporate inDICES voice to the policy discussion within the EIT community (NISV, FCC, EFHA, FBK).
- **RECHARGE project** - some of the inDICES partners are involved in this Horizon Europe initiative and will ensure the inDICES policy recommendations are taken into account in the design of the RECHARGE business models relying on sustainable participation in CHIs (Platoniq, EFHA, NISV, FCC).
- **Policy Recommendation Toolkit on the Open Observatory** - inDICES policy recommendations have also been published as a [participatory process](#) on the Open Observatory allowing us to present them in a more easily accessible way as well as iteratively collect input on the proposed recommendations. This is further described in section 4.2.

EVENTS:

- **reCreating Europe Final Conference** (March 2023, Brussels) - final event of inDICES sister project, with European policy makers, advocates, copyright experts aimed at rethinking digital copyright law for a more culturally diverse, accessible and creative Europe. The event will serve as an opportunity to publicly share the inDICES and reCreating Europe joint manifesto: *The Public Mission of CHIs in the Digital Age: an Open Manifesto* and will offer space to discuss continuation of joint actions towards European policy makers (led by FCC, with KUL).
- **COMMUNIA's session** (March 2023, Berlin) - a policy event discussing the need to further strengthen the use of Public Domain, also in the heritage sector. FCC is COMMUNIA's full partner and will bring the inDICES analysis and legal recommendations to the forum (FCC, NISV).
- **Creative Commons Open Culture Roundtable** (May 2023, Lisbon) - an event gathering experts - advocates and policy makers from all over the globe - to devise strategies to drive policy action towards better sharing of cultural heritage, seeing open culture as a global public good (with a special focus on informing the UNESCO framework for culture). It will be a kick-off for a longer collaboration (FCC, EF).

Sustainability and Exploitation of inDICES Policy and Legal Recommendations	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: FCC Main contributors: KUL, FBK, EF, NISV, a number of external contributors
IP STATUS (who is the owner of)	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

the IP)	
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	Policy Brief: policy makers, CHI professionals, special interest groups such as CH networks, stakeholders collaborating with CHIs White Paper: copyright experts, policy makers, CH professionals
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	Two complementary policy documents, based on evidence and co-drafted by Europe-based experts to facilitate policy discussions on the public mission of CHIs empowering democratic, community-focused heritage sector, including participation practices linked to reuse of heritage collections.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	Both documents are insightful sources creating space for strategic policy discussions on the current and future position and role of CHIs operating in the blended physical and digital realm, based on their public mission, supporting active participation and various reuse models of digital collections.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	The policy work is presented on a dedicated Policy Recommendations Toolkit in the Open Observatory. The Policy Brief and the White Paper are also available on Zenodo. Both will be also changed into a booklet.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	As these are high-level policy documents, both can serve efficiently in the long term to support the ongoing discussion on the role and the mission of the CH sector in a digitally transformed realm. Especially in the context of access and use of digital collections, copyright reform and participatory and community-focused strategies in CHIs.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Possible scenarios: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - present the recommendations and findings during professional events; - promote both documents using the power of the professional networks involved in inDICES; - turn the documents into publications; - build on the findings in next projects, e.g. RECHARGE and ongoing professional collaborations within partner networks or organisations, e.g. COMMUNIA, Creative Europe, individual consortium members of reCreating Europe, Knowledge Rights 21.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	Human effort and dedication, as well as budget to attend professional policy events is a must to continue building on the inDICES policy work. The next actions will rely on partners' individual interests and resources coming from external to inDICES funding - projects or own budgets.

4.2 Community Resources for Participatory Activities

Over the course of the project, inDICES partners have initiated a large number of participatory activities on the Open Observatory built around various research inquiries and outputs. These have been structured along four categories presented on the homepage of the Open Observatory to provide an easy gateway for the platform's visitors:

- OBSERVE the data and trends that are transforming the European Cultural Heritage;
- EXPLORE practical tools and resources to support your digital transformation;
- LEARN how to facilitate creative reuse and consumption of your digital cultural resources;
- PARTICIPATE to engage and connect with cultural heritage practitioners and communities across Europe.

Partners focused on making research findings easily accessible by translating them into short, easily consumable segments and initiating various participatory processes around them to stimulate further dialogue. An example of this is the Change Impact Assessment Framework produced by WP1. The full document is available via the inDICES Zenodo account⁴⁷ but it has also been transformed into a participatory process.⁴⁸ Each chapter of the document is presented as a separate section. The main focus of this research output is the eight impact areas presented as individual pages.⁴⁹ The platform's Proposal feature was used to set up space to collect case studies for the described impact areas. Each case study is tagged with relevant impact areas and is visualised on the map demonstrating their geographic distribution (see figure 2).

⁴⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7566478>

⁴⁸ https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes_groups/1

⁴⁹ <https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes/eightimpactareas>

Figure 2: Participatory process for the Change Impact Assessment Framework on the Open Observatory.

<https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes/casestudies/f/168/>

Different participatory activities will require varying degrees of efforts to ensure their sustainability and exploitation. A shared governance approach has been agreed on by the consortium where different partners take ownership and lead on specific activities. The table below presents a comprehensive overview of all the activities and strategies for their exploitation and sustainability.

Participatory Activity	Description & Strategy towards Exploitation and Sustainability
Change Impact	Description: a theoretical tool which guides cultural heritage institutions in

<p>Assessment Framework</p>	<p>assessing the positive impacts of their participatory activities in the digital sphere. It explains the theoretical foundations for impact assessment, offers theoretical recommendations for its implementation and provides a space to collect case studies of the proposed impact areas that can serve as an inspiration for others.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: cultural heritage practitioners, researchers, students, policy makers.</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: EFHA, FBK, NISV.</p> <p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: Partners will promote the use of the framework within ongoing and future projects (e.g. Europeana Impact Framework, RECHARGE, <i>ekip</i>). They will take the leading role in populating the collection of case studies and invite other stakeholders to do so. As the collection grows, we foresee that it can become of particular interest to researchers and policy makers who require evidence-driven strategies to demonstrate the impact of digital cultural heritage.</p>
<p>Copyright Guide</p>	<p>Description: an environment providing for heritage professionals with practical guidance on how to navigate the complex IPR legislation in their daily work. Through user participation, the Guide will develop by addressing user stories linking them to existing resources on copyright in the cultural sector.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: cultural heritage practitioners (especially those dealing with practical questions and policies around providing access to digital collections).</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: NISV, EF.</p> <p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: The Copyright Guide will be actively used during the Europeana Copyright Office Hours⁵⁰ to gather up-to-date user stories from heritage professionals dealing with copyright questions. It will be shared by consortium partners via networks such as Creative Commons Copyright platform, OpenGLAM and COMMUNIA.</p>
<p>inDICEs Datasets Assembly</p>	<p>Description: a space to aggregate datasets that support the analysis and understanding of digital cultural heritage reuse and participatory engagement with online culture.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: researchers, cultural heritage practitioners.</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: FBK.</p> <p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: The Datasets Assembly will continue to serve as a valuable space for researchers to deliberate on the datasets they will collect in their future research activities. This platform will allow them to engage in collaborative discussions, share information, and gain insights into the complex dynamics of cultural digitalization.</p>
<p>Hypotheses and Insights Assembly</p>	<p>Description: a space to propose and develop hypotheses around research questions relating to digital heritage reuse and participatory engagement with digital culture. This assembly is connected to the above described inDICEs Datasets Assembly - the data there can feed the development of hypotheses and vice versa - the proposed hypothesis will point to the need for data that can help to answer the raised questions.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: researchers, cultural heritage practitioners.</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: FBK, Platoniq.</p>

⁵⁰ <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/announcing-the-2023-copyright-and-policy-office-hours>

	<p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: The Hypothesis and Insights Assembly will serve as a central space for researchers to showcase their latest scientific findings and invigorate their ongoing research efforts. Through this regular engagement, the partners aim to leverage their collective knowledge, promote user engagement, and generate new insights into the intricate interplay between digital technologies and cultural heritage. By regularly sharing their scientific results and ideas, the partners can foster collaboration and advance their research efforts towards a more holistic understanding of the subject matter.</p>
<p>Policy Recommendations Toolkit</p>	<p>Description: a participatory activity built around the inDICES policy recommendations “Towards Community-Focused Cultural Heritage Institutions Operating in the Digital Realm”. It presents the proposed recommendations and provides a way to collect feedback on them via a survey mechanism. This allows us to iteratively collect feedback from cultural heritage practitioners on the usefulness of the recommendations, which can then inform future policy discussions and the implementation of the proposed actions.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: cultural heritage practitioners, heritage networks, policy makers at the EU and national level.</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: FCC.</p> <p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: For each policy recommendation area, a survey has been set up to collect input on their usefulness. Partners will promote the survey during their policy-related discussions and will use it as a reference in their policy activities.</p>
<p>Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation</p>	<p>Description: a compilation of resources that present digital transformation guidelines for cultural heritage institutions.</p> <p>Target stakeholders: cultural heritage practitioners, students in the heritage field.</p> <p>Partner(s) responsible: KUL, NISV.</p> <p>Actions towards sustainability and exploitation: The guidelines will be actively used by KUL in their educational programming. Partners will also aim to include (and if necessary update) the guideless in future projects that involve capacity building for heritage professionals. NISV will take the lead in continuously updating an overview of self-assessment tools to support digital transformation of heritage organisations.</p>

The table below provides a high-level summary of exploitation and sustainability path for the above described resources for participatory activities.

Sustainability and Exploitation of inDICES Policy and Legal Recommendations	
<p>PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)</p>	<p>Leading: Open Observatory Ambassadors Main contributors: all partners</p>
<p>IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)</p>	<p>Unless stated otherwise, all content of the participatory activities is published under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence</p>
<p>TARGET MARKET (stakeholders)</p>	<p>Different participatory activities have been tailored to meet the</p>

who need to be engaged, audience)	needs of different target groups. This includes: CH professionals (including practitioners and managers), students training to work in the sector, representatives from special interest groups (such as heritage networks, initiatives advocating for open culture and heritage reuse, etc.), researchers, policy makers, creative industry representatives.
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	A range of activities that facilitate collaboration and learning opportunities through participatory processes.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The responsible partners will activate their networks to take part in the described activities and will help to facilitate participation; - Complementary initiatives and projects where the activities could be used have already been identified.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	All activities are hosted on the Open Observatory platform. Some of the supporting materials are hosted on the project Zenodo account. Datasets proposed for the inDICES Datasets assembly are not hosted on the platform, only a reference to the location where they can be found (e.g. github) is provided.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	This will largely depend on the long-term strategy for the hosting of the Open Observatory (see section 5.1.1).
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Partners responsible for various activities, with the support from the Open Observatory Ambassadors, will facilitate participation in these activities and identify opportunities to engage relevant communities.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	Human resources and time (mainly for the Open Observatory Ambassadors) to moderate and facilitate participatory activities.

4.3 Datasets

Along the course of the inDICES project we explored several alternative sources of data that could help stakeholders of different types such as CH practitioners, researchers and policy makers, in reaching a quantitative understanding of the criticalities and opportunities associated with the rapid development of digital culture. We identified a number of datasets that could be used for describing the complex modern scenarios of the digitisation of cultural access. This includes a series of datasets collected by FBK and the News and Web content and social media data gathered by WLT that is accessible through the inDICES Visual Analytic Dashboard (VAD) Pro and Lite.

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A lot of the collected data comes with strong limitations to their free circulation (see D1.2 and D1.6 for details). For all cases where providing access to the data, as originally gathered or elaborated, was possible we provide a link through a specific assembly created inside the Hypothesis and Insight assembly of the Open Observatory. In some cases, it was not possible to share data but we provided the code necessary to get first hand access to the data source. The data collected by WLT is available in an aggregated form through the visualisations of the VAD Lite and as time-sliced data exports in the Pro version.

It is our hope that putting the data access at the root of the Hypothesis and Insight assembly will allow for a growing interest in the participation in the Open Observatory, allowing for a continued long term attention around the results of our project.

Sustainability and Exploitation of inDICES Datasets	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: FBK Main Contributors: WLT, Platoniq.
IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	The IP status of the datasets collected by FBK varies case by case and is described in detail in D1.2 and D1.6. The data collected by WLT is only shared in an aggregated form and through data visualisations via the inDICES Dashboard Pro and Lite.
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	CHIs practitioners, researchers and policy makers
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	By leveraging data-driven insights, inDICES enables stakeholders to study and understand the complex interplay between digital technologies and cultural heritage, driving innovation and growth in the cultural sector.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	The datasets are specifically highlighted in the inDICES Open Observatory Platform, in particular in the inDICES Dataset Assembly embedded into the Hypothesis and Insight Assembly. Datasets can be linked to specific hypotheses proposed or insight obtained from their analysis. Within the Open Observatory, the discussion can grow as new insights and new datasets are inserted, and users can engage by accessing them, when IP status allows, or download them using the code we developed in other cases. The data collected by WLT is accessible through the inDICES Dashboard Lite that is embedded in the Open Observatory and can be used for content exploration and to analyse the public debate and online publications of GLAMs and cultural and heritage institutions. Consortium members as well as interested stakeholders can additionally request access to the Pro version that offers full customization and advanced analytics.

HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	The datasets are indexed in the inDICES Dataset Assembly, but in most cases the user is directed to the original repository or to the use of an API facilitated by the sharing of the code used in our analysis. The VAD is hosted by WLT and accessible via the Open Observatory.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	From an academic perspective some of the datasets will have a long term interest. The data collected by WLT is also of long term interest. The inDICES dashboard Pro and Lite will continue to be maintained and the data collections kept running beyond the project's official end, but no further development efforts will be carried out.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Keeping animated the discussion in the Open Observatory Hypothesis and Insight assembly, and the embedded Datasets Assembly.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	Human effort is needed to keep the Open Observatory Hypothesis and Insight assembly active and alive; ideally, it could become a space where relevant scientific insights about Digital Culture are discussed and exchanged. WLT will continue to keep the VAD running and maintained for dissemination after the project ends. Maintenance costs are minimal and were factored into the budget plan.

4.4 MOOC

The inDICES Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) titled “Developing digital transition strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions” aims to support cultural organisations and professionals in understanding the potential of Digital Transformation in the cultural sector and in developing a digital strategy.⁵¹ It is primarily addressed to professionals in the cultural industry and students of digital cultural heritage.

A MOOC is an academic course which does not presuppose participation criteria or a participation fee. Contrary to generic Open Educational Materials, it requires a real study effort. It includes learning activities and is based on learning goals. This way, participation is more intense and requires a higher commitment than just downloading materials from a web source. In this way it is not only a great tool for universities to expand their educational activities to a wider audience, but it is also a good instrument to build bridges between academic and professional networks. This is precisely what we have done in the InDICES MOOC, which has been built with the help of the inDICES partner organisations. A second advantage of a MOOC is that it can deliver important learning contents outside of a regular curriculum, so that more innovation-oriented and timely content can be addressed.

⁵¹ <https://www.edx.org/course/developing-digital-transition-strategies-for-cultural-heritage-institutions>

For KUL, the exploitation of the MOOC resides in strengthening sector partnerships, as we have done in inDICES, and extending our reach through collaboration with sector organisations. It also allows us to address a “postgraduate” audience of somewhat more mature students (the average age of participants is mostly > 22). The sustainability of a MOOC depends on the strength of the network embedding it, as has been shown in previous KUL MOOC experience.

Sustainability and Exploitation of inDICES MOOC	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: KUL Contributors: all partners
IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	Contributing partners agreed to share the contents under CC-BY licence.
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	Professionals in the CH sector interested in Digital Transformation. Employers in the sector who want to offer training to their employees. Universities who use the MOOC as part of their educational materials in courses related to cultural heritage.
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	A training resource for CH professionals providing a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of digital transformation in the sector and how CHIs can harness its potential.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	The MOOC is an excellent instrument to deliver project impact and establish relationships with CH institutions in the sector. Several institutions actually requested that employees follow the MOOC. This could be encouraged further through the inDICES partners’ networks (Europeana, NEMO, etc.).
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	It is hosted on the KULeuvenX platform https://www.edx.org/school/kuleuvenx
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	KU Leuven has committed to launch the MOOC as an active course twice a (academic) year for 3 years. After 3 years, updates and revisions might be required. The archives version can stay online longer.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Uptake and promotion through Europeana Network Association and the Europeana Aggregators Forum (National / Domain aggregators) is key. KUL will actively promote the MOOC to its students in heritage-related subjects. All partners have committed to promote and include it in their future capacity building activities.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	KUL will keep staff resources allocated for the next 3 years, as maintenance and monitoring only require minimal effort.

5 Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy of Technological Assets

5.1 inDICES Open Observatory

The Open Observatory Platform is an online platform that facilitates collaboration, transparent deliberation and collective learning tailored around the topic of digital cultural heritage and digital transformation. Three key components constitute the unique selling proposition (USP) of the platform:

- **Participatory Space** - a collection of digital tools (e.g. surveys, proposal, etc.) and spaces (e.g. assemblies, processes) that facilitate participatory and data-driven processes. These have been set up by the inDICES consortium to facilitate collective decision-making processes, data collection in a bottom-up way and learning moments. A detailed description of participatory activities and resources that have been set up on the Participatory Space and how they will be maintained has been presented in section 4.1 Community Resources for Participatory Activities. The current chapter will focus on the sustainability and exploitation of the Participatory Space as an element of the larger infrastructure of the inDICES Open Observatory;
- **Visual Analytics Dashboard (VAD) Lite** - a set of data visualisation tools integrated into the Open Observatory. They serve two main purposes; (i) contextualising proposals and debates on the platform with content from external sources (websites, social media), and (ii) monitoring discussions in the media related to digital cultural heritage (e.g. digital transformation, decolonisation, etc.). VAD Lite is a simplified version of the full VAD tool which will be discussed in section 5.2;
- **Self-Assessment Tool (SAT)** - an interactive data collection and monitoring tool aimed at building digital transformation capacity through questionnaire and tailored recommendations. It has been designed as a flexible framework that could support data-collection activities in different contexts. During the course of the project, SAT framework was used to run the [Europeana ENUMERATE survey in 2022](#) as well as support community engagement activities during various events (for instance, a version of SAT created for the [Europeana Conference in 2022](#)).

In sections that follow, we describe in detail the proposed exploitation and sustainability strategy for the Open Observatory as a whole as well as for its individual components.

5.1.1. *Open Observatory Infrastructure*

After the end of the project, the Open Observatory with all of the above described components will remain freely available as a standalone platform. All the activities, tools as well as governance instruments that have already been set up will ensure that the platform is being actively used. It will remain hosted on Platoniq's servers.

At the conceptualisation of the inDICES proposal in 2019, it was envisioned that an integration between the Open Observatory and the Europeana Core Services Platform would be desirable. During the course of the project, partners explored what such an integration would mean (e.g. an option of creating a shared login for the Europeana Pro website and the Open Observatory). It became evident that such a tight integration between the two platforms would require significantly more resources than originally envisioned and would compromise the project's roadmap. Thus it was decided to opt for a lighter integration where the Open Observatory remains as a standalone platform but can be linked to from European Pro, the well-visited website operated by Europeana Foundation with comprehensive resources targeted at heritage professionals. Europeana Pro already offers a wealth of information (including the Europeana Impact Framework and Europeana Licensing Framework) that inDICES has built on.

Several inDICES consortium partners (ICCU, PLATONIQ, NISV, KUL, EF, EFHA) have committed to take on the role of **Open Observatory's Ambassadors**⁵², responsible for its long-term operations (including governance), stimulating engagement of already existing users as well as attracting new audiences. These partners are working on initiatives and projects closely related to the activities on the Open Observatory and have a direct benefit from its continued operation. Given this, Ambassadors fulfil their role on a voluntary basis.

These consortium members have been given administrative rights to manage content on the platform, and have been trained to use the platform as advanced users as well as to onboard others. Therefore, after the end of the project, ambassadors have all the knowledge and means to make sure that it is possible to set up new participatory activities. Ambassadors will also take on the responsibility of monitoring, updating and upholding community engagement guidelines, moderating content, granting/revoking permissions, answering questions from users.

To ensure efficient governance, the ambassadors will meet online at least once every quarter and communicate on a regular basis via a shared Basecamp environment (provided in kind by NISV). A schedule has been designed to share the platform's monitoring responsibilities on a rotating basis. The Ambassador

⁵² <https://participate.indices-culture.eu/assemblies/ambassadorAssembly>

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assembly will be responsible for crafting the principles and terms of their cooperation, including addressing points such as collective decision making and dispute resolution. At yearly intervals the group will assess the progress of the platform. No later than two years after the close of the project, the Ambassadors will undertake a feasibility assessment of the platform and determine if they intend to renew their role of Ambassador. As new platform users become more advanced and take on more administrative roles, they will be invited to take on ambassador roles. As the group expands over time, further governance instruments will be put in place to ensure continued clarity in roles and responsibilities.

The costs for maintaining the platform on Platoniq's servers will be limited to the costs of hosting and performing minor updates. If new technical features are required, Platoniq has committed to remain available to discuss new ideas, develop new projects, create new functions or processes, etc. This service would come at an additional cost.

Additionally, further developments in recent years have presented new options for the long-term exploitation and sustainability of the platform. In particular, two specific paths will be explored in the first year after the end of the project by the Open Observatory's platform ambassadors:

Path 1: Community collaboration tool for the Europeana Network Association. In 2022, the Europeana DS consortium (led by EF and including EFHA, NISV and MCA as partners) won the tender to deploy the common European data space for cultural heritage.⁵³ Among other things, this initiative will extend the existing Europeana infrastructure with new features for community engagement and capacity building via online tools. The Open Observatory could offer various functionalities to support this (e.g. through assemblies, SAT, proposals, etc.). Work is planned in the first half of 2023 to research and understand the needs of professionals within the Europeana network and the requirements for a community collaboration tool or platform. If the Open Observatory matches these needs, it will be proposed as one of the options. Since it is freely available, it can be used to trial some of the envisioned community interactions.

If a decision is made to choose the Open Observatory for the community collaboration tool for the Europeana network, Platoniq remains interested and available to perform the necessary technical development and integration work. When considering integration, two options can be considered: (i) transferring the inDICES instance to the EF servers, thus making EF autonomous in the maintenance (in this case Platoniq will make the service ready for delivery and support with the deployment and configuration process), or (ii) Platoniq will maintain the platform on their servers and EF would use it as a third-party

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<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-wins-tender-to-deploy-the-common-european-data-space-for-cultural-heritage>

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service. In this case Platoniq assumes the role of technical provider for EF) and a Service Level Agreement (SLA) with Europeana Foundation will have to be signed.⁵⁴

Path 2: Integration with RECHARGE. RECHARGE is a Horizon Europe (2022-2025) project with the goal to reinvigorate the cultural heritage sector with novel participatory business models.⁵⁵ Several inDICES project partners - NISV, CC, EFHA and Platoniq - are part of this new consortium and, just like inDICES, the project is built around an instance of the Decidim platform. As such, it already benefits from various technical improvements that have been introduced during inDICES (see more details about the extensions of the Decidim software in section 5.3). Since RECHARGE will build on certain aspects of the inDICES research (e.g. connecting the [Eight Impact Areas of Digital Cultural Participation](#) with participatory business models developed in RECHARGE), content and activities related to these aspects could be transferred to the RECHARGE platform. A Memorandum of Understanding has been signed between the two projects to ensure successful collaboration (see Annex 1 for the list of the agreed coordinated activities between the two projects).

Sustainability and Exploitation of the inDICES Open Observatory	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: Platoniq. Responsible for the technical development and maintenance of the platform for the duration of the project. Participating: All consortium partners as content contributors and ambassadors with admin roles.
IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	The Open Observatory is based on the software Decidim ⁵⁶ , and the licence remains under the GNU Affero General Public Licence terms. ⁵⁷ This licence forces any derivative work to be shared under the same terms, therefore, the source code of the platform is published in a Github repository. ⁵⁸ In case of further changes will be reported in the next iteration of this deliverable.
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Europeana Network Association (almost 4,000 members) and specifically its various communities and task forces, as well as thematic, domain and national Aggregators; - European cultural heritage organisations; - Policy makers and decision makers in the cultural heritage field; - Special interest groups (cultural heritage network, related projects); - Researchers in the field of digital cultural heritage;
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP)	An open online space with tools to facilitate transparent dialogue

⁵⁴ As the [Playbook for software development and integration](#)

⁵⁵ <https://recharge-culture.eu/>

⁵⁶ <http://decidim.org>

⁵⁷ <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html>

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/Platoniq/decidim-indices>

towards the target market)	and decision making processes, community-driven knowledge sharing and learning and concentration of actions towards shared goals.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	The Participatory Space remains an open environment available for everyone to initiate various participatory processes. The project partners act as ambassadors to moderate this as well as attract various stakeholders to make use of the platform.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	The platform and all the data will remain hosted on Platoniq's servers. Platoniq will be responsible for any future migration planned and agreed by the inDICES consortium with external partners considered to be beneficial for the sustainability of the project's results.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	The Open Observatory will be maintained online at least for two years after the end of the project. During this period, the Open Observatory Ambassadors will take an active role in animating the platform, inviting new communities to initiate participatory activities. The two exploitation paths presented in the section above will also be explored in parallel.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All partners actively promote the use of the Open Observatory via their ongoing activities, projects, dissemination channels; - All partners actively seek out to identify communities that could benefit from using the Open Observatory; - Ambassadors moderate content, onboard new users of the platforms and help to shape participatory activities; - Ambassadors oversee the governance.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	<p>Foreseen costs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hosting costs - €1,200.00 per annum (Two dedicated servers for acceptance and production environments ensuring continuity of services and participation levels.). - Partner time investment in acting as the platform's ambassadors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - voluntary agreement from a number of consortium (ICCU, NISV, Platoniq, EFHA, EF) representatives to take on this role. <p>Additional costs for further development of the platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bundle of hours for support in the creation, management and evaluation of participation processes. And collaborative sessions for the design of new interactions on the platform - €3,500.00 per annum for 50 hours of work.

5.1.2. *Participatory Space*

The Participatory Space provides a toolkit of functionalities, including assemblies, debates and processes, that support participatory engagement between the platform's users. As new participatory functionalities are developed by Platoniq or other entities within the Decidim open source community, they can also be made available for the inDICES platform. The ambassadors assembly will discuss whether such new features could provide added value to the platform and should be made available for the platform's users.

The main resources required for the maintenance, exploitation and sustainability of the Participatory Space are the availability and commitment of the consortium partners to:

- Use various participatory activities in their ongoing and future activities - as described above in section 4.1 Community Resources for Participatory Activities;
- Invite other communities to use this space and provide onboarding for them - as described in section 4.1 Community Resources for Participatory Activities;
- Moderate the content - as described above, this will be done by the ambassadors on a rotating basis.

5.1.3. *Visual Analytics Dashboard (VAD) Lite*

Since the Open Observatory will be used by CH practitioners as well as researchers and policy makers, the web and social media data collected by partner WLT needs to be accessible in a straightforward and user-friendly manner. Since the professional version of the [inDICES Visual Analytics Dashboard \(VAD\)](#) (see section 5.2) requires in-depth understanding of its analytical features, a "VAD Lite" was introduced and subsequently improved throughout the project to fulfil the need for a non-expert content exploration tool. Established as an embeddable widget for the Participatory Platform, it became an integral part of the Open Observatory.

The VAD Lite is an interactive tool with a straightforward configuration process that allows the users of the Participatory Space to analyse the public debate and quickly assess the latest topics discussed in relation to CCIs and across European GLAM websites. "Decolonization", "Diversity", "Digital Culture" and "Copyright" were established as predefined quick-access bookmarks to guide users and help them get a deeper understanding of these important issues and their role in the news and cultural sectors. Content associated with the "Eight Impact Areas" of the inDICES project can be compared based on associated terms and related stories. Through the source categorization it is simple to understand how topics correlate with classical sectors of news reporting (politics, science, education etc.) and CCI areas (museums, libraries, arts,

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film/theatre etc.). The possibility to use own search terms and restrict content through filters, directly in the embedded version, makes the VAD Lite a flexible tool to better understand web and social media content.

As one of the three pillars of the platform, the VAD Lite integrates directly with the main goals, *observe, explore, learn*, of the Open Observatory. Through the participation space, users are encouraged to discuss their findings and hypotheses, based on the large amount of content that is made available in the VAD Lite. Since new content is continuously added in close to real time (to be kept up-to-date as part of post-project exploitation as well), current and arising issues can be discovered and shared with peers.

Through the inDICES VAD Lite, users of the inDICES Observatory are encouraged to explore online trends related to their work, follow current topics and understand trends and their impact on community and stakeholders. Various options for further customizations and automated reporting features are available to experienced users with a desire to delve deeper into the analytical capabilities of the Professional version.

Data visualisations such as *colour-coded tag clouds* and *keyword graphs* can be powerful tools for cultural practitioners to understand the thematic areas of cultural heritage that are most relevant to their work. By analysing and visualising data related to the eight impact areas, cultural practitioners gain valuable insights into trends and patterns in these areas that are becoming increasingly part of discussions around the cultural heritage whether it is sustainable economies or resilient societies.

Embedded into the platform's proposal making component, a tag cloud can also highlight the most commonly used terms in articles, reports, or other relevant sources, e.g. for practitioners who want to identify key themes and areas of interest. The system helps them write more informed proposals around the topic to propose collaborations in the hypothesis or data set assembly, or identify knowledge gaps where there may be opportunities for further exploration and innovation. Participants can also enrich their work by developing discussions and collaborations in assemblies, which promotes networking with other participants active on the platform.

Overall, the *Dashboard Lite* and embeddable instances of inDICES visualisations in the proposals component provide cultural practitioners with tools for understanding and exploring the complex and interconnected themes of cultural heritage. By using these tools to gain insights, practitioners can make more informed decisions about how to promote and preserve cultural heritage in a way that is meaningful and impactful.

The table summarising the IP status and exploitation path of VAD Lite alongside the description of the professional version of the VAD can be found in section 5.2.

5.1.4. *Self-Assessment Tool*

The inDICES Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) was conceived as an interactive environment where cultural heritage professionals can collaboratively learn how to convert digital ambitions into digital strategies and gather data to continuously monitor their performance. The concept of the tool has evolved throughout the course of the project to reflect recent developments in the field. First of all, we observed that a large number of self-assessment tools have emerged in a similar timeframe as the inDICES project.⁵⁹ This meant that the consortium had to consider the unique value proposition in relation to other already existing solutions. Secondly, in 2022 an opportunity emerged to combine efforts for the development of the inDICES SAT with the ENUMERATE campaign which is led by EF to benchmark digitisation, digital preservation and online access to cultural heritage in Europe.⁶⁰

In response to these two developments, it was decided to design SAT not as a static tool but rather as a flexible data collection framework that encourages user participation by providing personalised insights. It can be customised to support data collection activities in large campaigns (such as ENUMERATE, see below) or small scale events. Specifically for the latter, a lighter iteration - SAT Lite - was developed to enable users to easily implement SAT in data collection activities during workshops, conferences, etc. Open Observatory users with administrative rights are able to design their own SAT for their specific purposes. The SAT framework was already used for the ENUMERATE 2022 campaign, as part of various participatory activities on the Open Observatory and an exercise in capacity building workshops carried out by the consortium. A detailed description of the SAT and of the functionalities it offers can be found in deliverable D4.6 *Development and Integration of CHIs Self Assessment Tool*.

A version of the SAT was created to carry out the ENUMERATE survey in 2022. The goal was to give recommendations back to participants of the survey, based on their answers, and to collect data to be used in policy making (primarily by Europeana and stakeholders) and that would also represent a baseline for various measures or indicators of issues such as digital transformation. Using the SAT for a long survey increased its complexity and changed its focus to include data collection. Feedback was gathered from the participants of the 2022 survey and EF together with other consortium partners are using this data to improve the next version of the tool.

Based on feedback received, we know that participants enjoyed getting recommendations back after filling out their details. This confirmed for us that using a tool with added functionality is much more desirable

⁵⁹ inDICES partners developed an overview of commonly used self assessment tools here:

<https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes/SelfAssessmentandMonitoringStrategies/f/193/>

⁶⁰ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/enumerate>

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over a standard survey. Some areas for improvement were identified from this feedback, such as the need to address that participants could not view their answers once the survey had been completed, and that the survey itself was too long.

Platoniq and EF are working on the next version of the ENUMERATE SAT which will be broken into themes, topics and questions, where participants can fill in fewer topics and use the tool to find out more about e.g. digital transformation, without having to fill in every section. Participants also requested a benchmarking feature, so we are working on a lite version of this to join the recommendations, for the next release of the ENUMERATE SAT planned for April 2023. Europeana Foundation would prefer to use such a tool for ENUMERATE data collection over a more traditional survey and will continue to gather and analyse the data the tool collects and aim to make it available through the means of a dashboard by 2024.

During the course of the project, the SAT Lite has demonstrated to bring added value for upskilling purposes. For instance, it was used during workshops organised for NEMO and MCA networks aimed at building digital transformation capacity of heritage professionals in the field as well as master students who are preparing for a career in this domain. Therefore we foresee that it can be successfully integrated in sectoral capacity building in the future. Moreover, since SAT is part of the components that is available for other Decidim instances, other communities using Decidim (e.g. municipalities) can adapt SAT for their own purposes. The SAT's complexity and content can be defined by the administrator, making it a versatile and effective way to gather information for administrators, and support organisational development, decision making, and overall performance.

Sustainability and Exploitation of the Self Assessment Tool	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: KUL, Platoniq Main contributors: EF, NISV.
IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	Published under the MIT Licence ⁶¹
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	The SAT targets any CH organisation that wants to assess where they stand in regards to Digital Transformation, in particular for looking at digitisation from a participatory viewpoint.
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	SAT presents a flexible framework for data collection, visualisation of insights and recommendation
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participatory activities on the Open Observatory platform; - Ongoing ENUMERATE data collection, as a tool for the survey; - Other communities (e.g. municipalities) using platforms based on

⁶¹ <https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>

	Decidim.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	SAT is part of the Open Observatory. All the collected data is hosted on the Platoniq servers.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	For as long as the tool is supported on the Open Observatory.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Partners will create their own SATs in ongoing and future projects to support data collection and capacity building activities. The Open Observatory Ambassadors will aim to identify opportunities where SAT could be used by different communities (e.g. to support workshops in events organised by heritage networks). Platoniq will promote its use by different communities (e.g. municipalities) using Decidim platform instances. KUL intends to use SAT Lite in regional workshops for heritage and CCI professionals.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	No additional financial resources needed. The maintenance of the SAT framework is ensured as part of the overall strategy for the maintenance of the Open Observatory (see above). Additional resources would be needed only if new features need to be added.

5.2 Visual Analytics Dashboard

One of the main assets developed is the inDICES Visual Analytic Dashboard (VAD) that is continuously updated with current news and social media feeds and offers the latest articles and updates of a large collection of GLAM and CHI websites. The stand-alone analytics dashboard is customised for cultural heritage content and supports cross-lingual queries, offers data visualisations and gives users insights into the latest trends in the sector, thereby helping them to reach their target audiences and increase the impact of their public relations & outreach activities. Its “Lite” version (presented in section 5.1.3) is one of the building blocks of the *Open Observatory* and provides a powerful content exploration tool that helps CH practitioners and stakeholders to analyse the public debate and follow trends in their sector. For more demanding and advanced users - such as researchers and data analysts in heritage organisations, the Pro version offers full customisation, advanced analytics and periodic reports.

Sustainability and Exploitation of the Visual Analytics Dashboard	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Leading: WLT Participating: All partners with feedback and input for desired content that provides added value for the target market.

IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	The inDICES dashboard is proprietary IP of WLT. Open access content is made available in an aggregated form via the embedded visualisations and the <i>VAD Lite</i> that is part of the inDICES Open Observatory platform.
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	CHI practitioners, policy makers, researchers, journalists and other stakeholders in the GLAM and CHI sectors.
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	A large repository of up-to-date content from websites and social media outlets from the CHI sector, analysed across multiple context dimensions and enriched with metadata (source categories, opinion leaders, geo locations, entities, sentiment & emotion etc.), supported by an evolving CHI Knowledge Graph, all accessible through the inDICES Visual Analytics Dashboard.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	All content is accessible via the inDICES Dashboard “Lite”, a data exploration tool that is part of the Open Observatory. Accessible as an embedded widget, platform users can directly and interactively explore the content and share and discuss findings with other users of the Open Observatory. The “Pro” version offers advanced functionalities and PDF reports targeting professional users.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	The inDICES Dashboard is part of the Open Observatory and hosted on WLT servers. The “Lite” version is accessible directly from the landing page of the Open Observatory, individual visual widgets to render metadata-enriched content are integrated into the participatory processes.
HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)	The inDICES dashboard and its main functionalities will be operated beyond the end of the project. Content flows will be kept alive so that the latest news and social media contents will be available. WLT plans to offer premium services to help maintain and further evolve the platform.
KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)	Extend and keep a large user base on the Open Observatory platform. Promote the final results of the project, encourage the use of the inDICES Dashboard Lite/Pro for CHI practitioners and stakeholders in their daily workflows, and prepare offers for post-project usage scenarios.
FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)	WLT will continue to keep the inDICES Analytics Dashboard Pro and Lite running and maintained for dissemination after the project ends. Ongoing maintenance costs will be kept low. Minor updates will be activated as part of WLT’s regular release cycles, more significant extensions will be financed through premium SaaS subscriptions services.

5.3 Extensions to the Decidim Open Source Software

Decidim is a digital platform for participatory democracy that can be used by a wide range of organisations and communities, including those focused on cultural heritage and GLAMs (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums). The platform is designed to facilitate democratic decision-making processes and promote citizen participation, so it is particularly relevant for organisations that prioritise community engagement and collaboration.

The use of Decidim for the inDICES Open Observatory has led to the creation of certain features and hacks that will be available to the wider Decidim community through Github. This includes:

- **Self-Assessment Tool (SAT):** The SAT is embedded in the inDICES Open Observatory that facilitates active engagement and knowledge sharing between CH professionals on topics related to digital transformation. It is specifically designed to engage participants in debates, brainstorming and community building activities;
- **SAT Lite**, a variation of the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) that allows administrators to create their own self assessment tools in which users will be able to receive recommendations based on their responses to customised surveys developed by the administrator. The SAT Lite is an iteration of the original SAT tool (SAT Enumerate) and its development was inspired by specific resources developed by WP3 in D3.3 DSM readiness assessment Methodology and the related Infoccharts. As a result, the questions for the SAT Lite include images and strive for a more visual approach to surveys that might make it easier to engage with participants and provide more context to each question. SAT Lite has been used to design the Open Observatory Onboarding Quiz. See D4.6 Development and Integration of CHI's Self Assessment Tool;
- **Notify;** A note-taker feature focused on conversations. This module provides a component for any participatory space in Decidim;
- Custom fields for proposals Admins can substitute the body of a proposal with a set of form fields. Edition is made with a Drag & Drop interface in the admin and can be scoped to apply only to proposal components;
- inDICES also has contributed to the **Decidim Awesome** Module by Platoniq that allows to improve usability and UX tweaks for Decidim. This plugin allows the administrators to expand the possibilities of Decidim beyond some existing limitations. All tweaks are provided in an optional fashion with granular permissions that let the administrator choose exactly where to apply those mods. Some tweaks can be applied to any assembly, others in specific participatory processes.

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- inDICES has contributed to the improvement of the AlternativeLanding module, which allows the deployment of additional Content Blocks for Decidim.

The creation of new tools and features on Decidim supports the strength of the software and the availability of tools within the larger open source community. Finally, supporting the use of Decidim encourages the use of more ethical open source software that is not beholden to corporate capture whether in terms of proprietary software or participants data.

Sustainability and Exploitation of the Extension to the Decidim Open Source Software	
PARTNERS INVOLVED (who were involved along the process)	Platoniq.
IP STATUS (who is the owner of the IP)	Decidim is an open-source digital platform for participatory democracy that is managed by the Decidim development community. The IP of Decidim belongs to the community, and it is governed by a free software licence (GNU AGPLv3), which means that the software can be used, modified, and distributed freely by anyone. Therefore, there is no single owner of the Decidim IP. Instead, it is collectively owned and managed by the community of developers, contributors, and users who contribute to its ongoing development and improvement.
TARGET MARKET (stakeholders who need to be engaged, audience)	The main target market for the newly developed Decidim features are local governments or municipalities that are already using Decidim instances to facilitate participatory processes. These organisations use the platform to engage with stakeholders in decision-making processes, including those related to the management and preservation of cultural heritage assets. Features such as Decidim Awesome, a suite of features to tweak and customise platforms, is already widely used from the Decidim platform in New York to Brussels Parliament.
VALUE PROPOSITION (USP towards the target market)	The unique value proposition of Decidim is its social contract that commits all the community to transparency, traceability, and accountability to its participant users. Additionally, it is an instance of platform software developed for public participation but public entities and resources. Finally, it offers multiple features that rethink how participation and engagement work online that are not designed around competing for screen time of its users but genuinely engaging them in open, transparent participation and decision making.
EXPLOITATION PATHS (how will the stakeholders / audiences use/engage with the outcome)	Stakeholders will be able to adapt or integrate features developed for Decidim within the inDICES project into their own platforms and adapt and reuse them for participatory activities and processes.
HOSTING (how and where can it be accessed?)	The outcome of the features adapted to Decidim will live on Github as available code to the wider community of Decidim users.

<p>HOW LONG (for how long can this outcome be used and relevant for the target market?)</p>	<p>The relevance of a feature developed on Decidim will depend on a variety of factors, including the nature of the feature itself, the needs and preferences of the users, and the evolving landscape of technology and digital platforms.</p> <p>Some features may be more long-lasting than others. For example, features related to the basic functionality of the platform, such as survey templates or the self assessment tool which gives feedback based on data from the survey component may be less likely to become outdated than features related to specific content areas or functionalities.</p> <p>However, by prioritising user needs and preferences, and by keeping up-to-date with evolving technologies and platforms, Decidim can help to ensure that its features remain relevant and useful for its users over time.</p>
<p>KEY ACTIONS (how to ensure interest in and engagement with the outcome?)</p>	<p>Keeping stakeholders interested in features developed on Decidim now in the future can be achieved through a variety of strategies, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant and administrator feedback: Soliciting user feedback on features developed on Decidim can help to ensure that they remain relevant and useful to stakeholders over time; - Regular improvements: Updating and improving features developed on Decidim can help to keep stakeholders engaged and interested in the platform demonstrating its commitment to innovation and its ability to adapt to changing user needs and preferences; - Capacity building and support: Providing training and support resources for users can help to ensure that they are able to use features developed on Decidim effectively; - Community building: Fostering a sense of community among stakeholders can help to keep them interested in features developed on Decidim over time. This can be achieved through a variety of strategies, including social media engagement, user forums, and in-person events.
<p>FINANCIAL (what resources are necessary to maintain it? for how long? where will the resources come from?)</p>	<p>Decidim extensions will be maintained and updated by an already established community of open source developers working with Decidim. Companies who support the set up of Decidim platform instances for various stakeholders, for instance, municipalities, will be able to use the catalogue of the newly added features as needed.</p>

6 Strategy for the inDICES Brand

The exploitation and sustainability strategy presented in the chapters above focuses on individual exploitable assets rather than one consolidated product. Such a strategy has been chosen to ensure that the project's results can be exploited individually in different contexts and in formats most appropriate for the various target groups. This will ensure that the exploitable assets can be further developed in future projects and activities under different brands. Therefore as the project comes to the end, the inDICES brand will live as the legacy of the project.

6.1 inDICES Dissemination and Communication Channels

The inDICES brand was most prominently used across the project's dissemination and communication channels. This includes: the project's website, social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), newsletter and Zenodo account for research publications. These channels will be maintained online as the legacy of the project but will no longer be actively updated. Since there are no costs associated with the use of the Zenodo platform and social media channels, it is foreseen that they can be kept online for an undefined period of time. The website will be maintained for four years after the end of the project by NISV. After this period, it will be evaluated whether the website should be maintained or archived. In the case of the latter scenario, it will be archived using the Internet Archive repository as well as NISV's internal web archive. This will ensure that legacy information can still remain publicly accessible. At the end of the project, consortium partner NEMO will also create a dedicated page (forthcoming) on their website with links to inDICES research outputs relevant for museums and professionals in its network, in this way further supporting the exploitation of key exploitable assets via an additional dissemination channel.

After the end of the project, inDICES social media channels will be used periodically to promote the results of the project at opportune moments, highlight activities that emerge around the project's results and inform existing audiences about related initiatives that would be of interest to them. This way, a community that was built during the course of the project will be redirected to keep engaged with the topic through other projects and organisations.

6.2 Branding of the Open Observatory

Currently the Open Observatory is branded with the inDICES name and visual identity. As different exploitation paths for the platform are explored, it will be decided whether to maintain the current branding or opt for an alternative solution. For instance, in the scenario where the Open Observatory would

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be chosen as the collaborative platform to support the Europeana Network Association for the activities described in the Data Space for Cultural Heritage tender, the branding would be changed to that of Europeana.

7 Conclusions

As mentioned in Chapter 3, the Horizon 2020 Programme call addressed by inDICES set out to “contribute to a better understanding of regulation and fairer accessibility of digitised cultural goods and services. It will also advise on appropriate levels of harmonisation of copyright and IPR, thereby contributing to the development and deepening of the Digital Single Market.” As evidenced above, through its actions, inDICES delivered a variety of results directly contributing to this:

- Concrete and actionable policy and legal recommendations validated by relevant stakeholders proposing conditions that would (i) **propel the reuse of digital cultural heritage through an enhanced copyright system**, maximising the impact of public investments made towards digitisation in the last few decades, and (ii) enable CHIs to fulfil their public mission in the digital realm through **community-centred digital transformation strategies**;
- The Open Observatory platform with components that support (i) transparent deliberation processes to **collectively and iteratively shape the role of CHIs** in a digital society (Participatory Space), (ii) bottom-up data collection activities to **monitor the needs and capacities in the sector** and use them to inform policy- and decision-makers (Self Assessment Tool), and (iii) **data-driven analysis of trends and forces** that are influencing the operations of CHIs (Visual Analytics Dashboard);
- Knowledge resources (including the MOOC, the Change Impact Assessment Framework and the Copyright Guide) that aim to **upskill current and future CH professionals** and enable them to **navigate the constantly changing digital landscape** while **contributing to societal well-being** through activities that are carefully designed to achieve their impact.

The successful conclusion of inDICES as a project supported by Horizon 2020 also marks the start of the implementation of the exploitation and sustainability strategy. As highlighted below, the work will be carried forward, in several directions. For instance: activities of the Open Observatory Ambassadors who will animate the platform and stimulate engagement in participatory processes, further capacity building work that will be carried out by various consortium partners in the context on ongoing and new activities using resources developed by inDICES (such as the MOOC for university-level courses or the Copyright Guide for the Europeana Copyright Office Hours), or advocacy efforts in high-impact networks such as COMMUNIA to innovate legal and policy frameworks.

The context in which inDICES operated and contributed to is ever evolving. Chapter 3 highlights a number of legislative actions, policy directions and grassroots work that will shape the way cultural heritage will be

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accessed, analysed, enjoyed and reused. Over the past years, the inDICES consortium members sensed the enormous future potential of digital heritage, as more and more material is made available to an ever growing number of stakeholders. For this potential to be delivered, it is vital that policy makers adapt current copyright legislations, following legal recommendations put forward by the project and take measures to foster community-focused cultural heritage institutions that are fully equipped to live up to their public missions and deliver societal as well as economic impact. This will further cement the position of cultural heritage as a driving force to address some of today's biggest challenges, as articulated by the UNs Sustainable Development Goals. Notably, CHIs can play a key role in contributing towards quality education, economic growth, inclusive societies and reducing inequalities.

Given this, we encourage the European Commission to continue supporting the various stakeholders - CHIs, researchers, creative professionals and grassroot communities - that continuously redefine and investigate the role of digital cultural heritage. Support instruments put forward by programmes such as the EIT Culture and Creativity, New European Bauhaus, Horizon Europe, Creative Europe Media Programme and the European strategy for data are critical to this. inDICES consortium partners are eager to see and actively participate in further efforts to support a European public digital infrastructures and copyright reform that will strengthen the work and impact of cultural heritage institutions.

8 Annex 1

Memorandum of Understanding

between

inDICES and *RECHARGE*

Coordinated Activities

- Co-creation of a scenario to build on and incorporate relevant results developed by inDICES and hosted in the [inDICES Open Observatory](#) into the RECHARGE [Participatory Platform](#). Both platforms are based on the same open source infrastructure (Decidim) and the partner in charge of the technical development is the same (Fundación Platoniq - Goteo). For instance, this could include:
 - Preparation of shared resources to be published in the Participatory Platform by combining relevant results of the two projects (e.g. materials for the RECHARGE knowledge base, content for the RECHARGE Playbook etc.);
 - Elaboration of a roadmap to make the open source SAT Lite component (self-assessment tool) developed in inDICES which has been made available for use in RECHARGE and in all instances of Decidim.
- Participation in joint events and initiatives, such as the inDICES final event “Community and Digitisation: the new drivers of cultural heritage“ to be held in Rome on 2 March 2023.
- Promotion and presentation of the results of the concerned projects in the respective websites.
- Publication of articles on the work and results of the concerned projects in scientific journals and in sector specific online publications.
- Posting joint news on third party websites, newsletters and social media channels.
- Circulation of joint announcements/results via relevant mailing lists.